

I. DATA FROM THE PARTICIPANTS' INSTITUTIONS

TABLE I: Industry institutions

ID	Redesim	Census I	Census II	State
01	N/A	✓	N/A	SP
02	✓	N/A	✓	SE
03	✓	✓	✓	SC
04	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
05	✓	N/A	✓	RJ
06	N/A	N/A	✓	MA
07	✓	N/A	✓	RJ
08	✓	N/A	✓	MT
09	✓	N/A	N/A	RJ
10	✓	N/A	✓	SC
11	N/A	N/A	N/A	DF
12	✓	N/A	✓	DF
13	N/A	N/A	N/A	SP
14	N/A	N/A	N/A	BA
15	✓	N/A	✓	SP
16	✓	✓	N/A	PE
17	✓	N/A	✓	AM
18	✓	N/A	N/A	PR
19	N/A	N/A	✓	SC
20	✓	N/A	N/A	SP
21	N/A	N/A	N/A	SP
22	✓	✓	✓	RJ
23	✓	N/A	✓	RJ
24	✓	N/A	✓	RJ
25	✓	✓	✓	PR
26	N/A	N/A	N/A	PA
27	✓	N/A	N/A	RJ
28	✓	✓	✓	DF
29	✓	✓	N/A	SP
30	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
31	N/A	N/A	N/A	RJ
32	✓	N/A	N/A	RJ
33	✓	N/A	N/A	SP
34	N/A	N/A	N/A	RJ
35	✓	N/A	✓	SC
36	✓	N/A	N/A	PR
37	✓	N/A	✓	SP
38	✓	N/A	✓	SP
39	N/A	N/A	N/A	SP
40	✓	✓	N/A	SP
41	✓	N/A	N/A	RS
42	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
43	✓	N/A	✓	ES
44	N/A	N/A	N/A	RJ
45	N/A	N/A	N/A	PI
46	✓	N/A	N/A	SP
47	✓	N/A	✓	RN
48	✓	N/A	✓	RJ
49	✓	N/A	N/A	RJ
50	✓	N/A	✓	ES
51	✓	N/A	N/A	SP
52	✓	N/A	✓	SP
53	✓	N/A	✓	MA

TABLE I: Industry institutions (continued)

ID	Redesim	Census I	Census II	State
54	✓	N/A	✓	SP
55	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
56	N/A	N/A	✓	MG
57	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
58	N/A	N/A	N/A	ES
59	✓	N/A	✓	PI
60	✓	N/A	✓	RJ
61	✓	N/A	✓	SP
62	✓	✓	✓	AM
63	✓	✓	N/A	N/A
64	✓	N/A	N/A	MG
65	N/A	N/A	✓	SP
66	N/A	N/A	N/A	SP
67	N/A	N/A	✓	SP
68	N/A	N/A	✓	CE
69	N/A	N/A	N/A	RJ
70	✓	N/A	N/A	N/A
71	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
72	N/A	N/A	N/A	BA
73	✓	N/A	✓	MG
74	✓	N/A	✓	DF
75	N/A	N/A	N/A	AL
76	✓	✓	✓	BA
77	✓	N/A	✓	SP
78	✓	N/A	N/A	SP
79	N/A	N/A	N/A	RJ
80	✓	N/A	✓	SC

TABLE II: Academic institutions

ID	Research field	State
01	Digital games for public service; Digital games based on business processes;	RJ
02	Educational games;	CE
03	Game design;	ES
04	Accessibility in games; Computer engineering;	MG
05	Mathematics education and digital games; Games industry (programs and policies);	BA
06	Design illustration games;	RJ
07	Game design;	N/A
08	Games and AI;	SP
09	Serious games for treating phobias;	TO
10	Game design;	PE
11	Teaching game development;	SP
12	Game studies/communication;	PE
13	Programming and design;	SC
14	IT project management;	SC
15	Animation;	N/A
16	Gamification in education;	SP
17	Gamification in education;	SP
18	Rapid development of digital games;	SP
19	Digital gaming based on business processes;	MG
20	Digital games; Locative games;	MG
21	Games and Health;	RJ
22	Industry;	MS
23	Serious digital games;	ES

TABLE II: Academic institutions (continued)

ID	Research field	State
24	E-sports;	MG
25	Educational games;	MG
26	Artificial Intelligence;	SP
27	Technology applied to education; Rapid development of digital games;	SP
28	Gamification	RS
29	Computational neuroscience and development of assistive technologies to support the teaching-learning of children with TEA;	RN
30	Informatics, education and society;	RJ
31	Digital games;	N/A
32	Serious games; Animation, 3D modeling and ludic appropriation;	MG
33	Game content production; Game design and game development; Game development process;	SP
34	Game development process	SP
35	Game development process	SP
36	Games and Health; Gamer Motivation;	PR
37	Design;	RJ
38	Virtual reality;	RN
39	2D and 3D game programming, more focused on moba games;	PI
40	Game design; Digital games as educational devices and cultural mediators;	SP
41	Advertising;	MA
42	Game design and semiotics;	SC
43	Digital game design and development;	N/A
44	Game analytics;	DF
45	Accessibility;	CE
46	Programming; Education and digital games/game sports; Multifaceted procedural content generation via multiagent systems; Educational games and gamification;	SP
47	Games, Gamification and Health; Art and Games; Music Composition for Games;	BA
48	Art and games;	BA
49	Music composition for games;	BA
50	Exergame development by non-programmer researchers; Game development for drug addicts; Human computer interaction; Serious games;	SC
51	Virtual reality and augmented reality;	AM
52	Educational games;	RJ
53	Accessible digital games; Artificial intelligence;	SC
54	Game design and 3D art;	RJ
55	Production; Interaction in Extended Reality;	N/A
56	Digital games applied to autism;	BA
57	Serious Games for Health; Computer Science;	SP
58	Master in crowdsourcing; Computer graphics;	BA
59	Game design;	PB
60	Informatics in the education of deaf people;	AL
61	Digital games for people with physical disabilities in the upper limbs;	GO
62	Games and pain management/cardiology; Social communication/interaction design; Accessibility, human-computer interaction;	MG
63	Communication;	MG
64	Communication - immersion;	PE
65	Computer science; Education and communication; Teacher training for media use; Serious games; News games, games in communication, serious games;	SC
66	Artificial Intelligence;	MG
67	Educational and/or speech recognition games; Computer science;	SE
68	Computer networks and software engineering; Visual communication; Pervasive games; Artificial intelligence for games; Illustration and concept art; Human-computer interaction; Game studies; E-sports;	CE
69	Virtual and augmented reality; e-learning;	ES
70	Serious games for teaching programming; Visual representation in digital games; Engineering and knowledge management;	MA
71	Informatics in Education;	PA

TABLE II: Academic institutions (continued)

ID	Research field	State
72	Human-computer interaction, software engineering, digital games;	RS
73	Sound design; Scientific visualization, virtual reality, gamification; Game design; Motivational aspects of the player in educational digital games; Serious games;	PR
74	Psychology and games; Gamification of education; Serious games; Computer and information engineering; Game design and game studies;	RJ
75	Psychopedagogy and digital games/e-learning; Informatics in education; Graphic and sequential arts; Well-being of gamers; Virtual reality;	RS
76	2D platform level procedural generation;	RJ
77	Alzheimer's; Digital games;	SP
78	Multi-platform games; Digital games as educational devices and cultural mediators;	SP
79	Software engineering and computer science in education; Software engineering; Serious games;	PR
80	Graphic design; 3D modeling;	RJ